

Decentralized Currency Governance in BRICS+: Legal Mechanisms of Currency Cooperation

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Abstract

This article examines the legal regulation of currency cooperation within BRICS+. The study analyzes the hybrid legal nature of the association as a quasi-institutional format that combines soft law mechanisms with binding international agreements. Particular attention is paid to the legal role of the New Development Bank and the Contingent Reserve Arrangement, as well as to bilateral currency swap agreements between member states. The paper argues that BRICS is forming a decentralized model of monetary coordination based on contractual networking rather than supranational integration.

Keywords: BRICS; International Economic Law; Currency Cooperation; Soft Law

Introduction

BRICS represents one of the most significant forms of international interaction in the modern system of global governance. Its legal nature has generated scholarly debate, as the association does not conform to the classical model of an international intergovernmental organization. In academic literature, BRICS is often characterized as an international quasi-organization (Abashidze, 2012, p. 10) [1].

The lack of a rigid institutional structure determines the specific nature of legal regulation within the association. Decisions adopted at summits and ministerial meetings are primarily political in nature and fall within the sphere of “soft law.” This model reflects states’ caution in transferring sovereign powers while simultaneously ensuring flexibility in cooperation.

However, the institutional flexibility of BRICS should not be regarded as a weakness. As E. E. Rafalyuk notes, the diversity of legal cultures and legal systems among BRICS countries is not an obstacle but rather a resource for addressing complex challenges (Rafalyuk, 2024, p. 1). Flexibility serves as an adaptive mechanism for cooperation between states with different legal systems and levels of economic development. The soft-law model allows the formation of a common agenda without the creation of rigid supranational structures, thereby reducing the political and legal costs of integration. The existence of shared strategic development guidelines and mutual interest in outcomes creates a solid foundation for the voluntary implementation of agreements while avoiding excessive formalization and jurisdictional conflicts.

Monetary and financial cooperation is one of the most sensitive areas of interstate interaction. In this sphere, the combination of soft and contractual mechanisms is particularly visible: political declarations set strategic guidelines, while individual international agreements establish specific institutional instruments for cooperation.

Despite the growing academic interest in BRICS cooperation, the legal architecture of monetary coordination within the BRICS+ format remains insufficiently studied in international legal scholarship. Existing studies primarily focus on the political and economic dimensions of the association, while the interaction between soft law instruments, treaty mechanisms, and bilateral financial agreements has received significantly less attention. This article seeks to fill this gap by examining the multi-layered legal framework governing currency cooperation within BRICS+.

Principles of Legal Regulation of Cooperation

The legal regulation of cooperation between BRICS member states in the monetary and

[1] A format of institutionalized cooperation without a founding treaty, statute, permanent secretariat, headquarters, or international legal personality.

financial sphere is based on a complex multi-level system of principles that creates a unique legal environment for this association (Anufrieva, 2019, p. 127). This system integrates generally recognized imperative norms of general international law (jus cogens), special (sectoral) principles of international economic law and legal principles of cooperation developed directly within the BRICS framework.

The foundation consist of universally recognized principles of international law, which are consistently referenced in BRICS summit declarations. An analysis of BRICS declarations from 2009 to 2025 confirms the participants' commitment to the central role of the United Nations, the peaceful settlement of disputes, sovereign equality of states, and the idea of a just international order. These principles define the overall normative context for cooperation.

Another level is formed by the principles of international economic law. As I.S. Chabaeva notes, these include the principle of mutual benefit, the principle of the inalienable sovereignty of states over their resources and economic activity, the principle of economic non-discrimination, and the principle of freedom to choose the forms of organizing foreign economic relations (Chabaeva, 2010, p. 181). These principles ensure economic sovereignty and equality and are therefore fundamental for BRICS, whose activities are based on respect for the diversity of development models.

The third level consists of special political and legal principles of BRICS cooperation: – pragmatism, openness, solidarity, the non-aligned nature of the association and the principle of not directing its activities against third parties [2] (Russian Federation, 2013, p.3). These principles directly shape the model of monetary cooperation. For example, pragmatism and freedom of choice predetermine a project-based approach that focuses not on creating a supranational monetary union but on establishing specific institutions such as the New Development Bank (NDB) and the Contingent Reserve Arrangement (CRA).

This multi-layered combination of principles creates a flexible model of legal regulation that maintains a foundation in fundamental norms of international law while allowing states to cooperate without rigid institutional integration.

Soft Law Mechanisms

BRICS's activities in the area of monetary and financial cooperation rely heavily on soft law mechanisms, a direct consequence of its legal nature as a flexible international quasi-organization.

[2] These principles are an adaptation of the basic tenets of international economic law to the format of an informal association.

As E.E. Rafalyuk rightly notes, the sources of regulation within BRICS are primarily advisory acts [3], which shape the ideology and set strategic guidelines for cooperation. In the absence of a rigid supranational institutional structure, it is these documents that serve to consolidate the political will of member states and shape a common agenda.

These documents, while not formally legally binding, fulfill a number of critical functions. First, they consistently establish the strategic goals of cooperation [4]. Secondly, they form a political consensus among participating states and determine the direction of further initiatives [5].

It's important to note that the evolution of BRICS declarations demonstrates a gradual shift from political statements to the development of concrete cooperation mechanisms. While declarations previously focused on criticizing the shortcomings of the existing system [6], they are now gradually beginning to include agreements on practical steps (for example, exploring the possibility of creating new financial institutions) [7], which led to the signing of legally binding agreements on the NDB [8] and the CRA [9]. Thus, soft law acts act as a political and legal incubator in which ideas mature and are tested, only then receiving formal contractual registration.

This mechanism for implementing acts is called the “network horizontal regulation” model (Rafalyuk, 2024, p. 2) - agreements reached at the highest level are not imposed from above, but are translated into national legal systems through the inclusion of relevant tasks in development strategies, activity plans of ministries and central banks of member states [10].

International Treaty Mechanisms

In 2014, two key international treaties were signed, which today serve as the main legal

[3] For example, the final declarations of the BRICS summits of heads of state and government, joint communiqués and action plans

[4] For example, reforming the international monetary and financial system, expanding the use of national currencies, and strengthening financial stability.

[5] For example, calls for coordinated macroeconomic policy, development of regional financial markets, etc.

[6] UNITED STATEMENT OF THE HEADS OF STATE AND GOVERNMENT OF THE SECOND BRIC SUMMIT. (2010). Brasilia, Brazil, 15 Apr. 2010; BRICS SANYA DECLARATION. (2011). Sanya, China, 14 Apr. 2011.

[7] FORTALEZA DECLARATION. (2014). BRICS Sixth Summit Declaration. Fortaleza, Brazil, 15 July 2014.

[8] RUSSIA. Agreement on the New Development Bank. Fortaleza, 15 July 2014. Bulletin of International Treaties, Moscow, n. 3, p. 3–44, Mar. 2016. Available at: <http://www.pravo.gov.ru>. Accessed on: 10 Mar. 2026.

[9] TREATY FOR THE ESTABLISHMENT OF THE BRICS CONTINGENT RESERVE ARRANGEMENT. (2014). Bulletin of International Treaties, Moscow, n. 10, p. 5–24, Oct. 2020.

[10] For example, the goal of increasing mutual settlements in national currencies, repeatedly proclaimed in declarations (Kazan Declaration of BRICS, October 23, 2024), is realized through the conclusion of bilateral agreements (See, for example, the Agreement between the Government of the Russian Federation and the Government of the People's Republic of China on settlements and payments of June 5, 2019; the Agreement between the People's Bank of China and the Central Bank of Brazil on currency swaps of May 14, 2025.) and the development of infrastructure within each country.

regulators of currency cooperation within BRICS: the Treaty on the Establishment of the Contingent Reserve Arrangement and the Agreement on the New Development Bank.

The Contingent Reserve Arrangement Agreement is a classic intergovernmental agreement that creates a mechanism for mutual financial support among participating states in the event of short-term balance of payments problems. The legal structure of the agreement reflects a pragmatic approach that takes into account the different economic potential of the participants [11]. The Pool's legal structure is highly decentralized. It does not establish a separate international organization with a developed institutional structure, but functions as a system of mutual commitments among states to provide funds. Thus, it becomes the first legally binding financial security instrument, reducing the BRICS countries' dependence on external sources of liquidity.

New Development Bank [12], by contrast, is a fully-fledged international organization created to finance infrastructure projects and sustainable development. From a monetary cooperation perspective, its significance is fundamental. First, it is based on the principle of equal shares in authorized capital, which is a direct institutional implementation of the declared sovereign equality and contrasts with the weighted voting model of the IMF and the World Bank. Second, the NDB actively promotes national currency policies, financing projects in rubles, yuan, and rupees and issuing bonds on local markets. This creates practical demand for BRICS currencies and develops their infrastructure. Third, the Agreement's openness to new members, while maintaining a controlling stake of at least 55% for the original five, creates the legal basis for the "BRICS+" format, allowing these currency practices to be scaled up to a wider range of countries.

Together, the CRA and the NDB form a complementary legal framework that transforms currency cooperation from a declaratory to an operational level, opening the door to deeper currency integration. While the Pool serves as a shock absorber for short-term shocks and a safety net, the Bank drives long-term de-dollarization and investment in national currencies.

Bilateral And Interbank Agreements

Along with multilateral mechanisms, bilateral currency agreements between BRICS countries and interbank agreements play an important role. This level of legal regulation is currently demonstrating the most dynamic development and creates a real foundation for the transition to integrative trends in currency cooperation.

[11] The total commitment is US\$100 billion, with contributions distributed asymmetrically: China - US\$41 billion, Brazil, Russia and India - US\$18 billion each, and South Africa - US\$5 billion.

[12] MINISTRY OF FOREIGN AFFAIRS OF THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION. (2014). Agreement on the New Development Bank. Bulletin of International Treaties, Moscow, n. 3, p. 3-44, Mar. 2016. Available at: <http://www.pravo.gov.ru>. Accessed on: 08 Mar. 2026.

For example, the Currency Swap Agreement between Russia and China, which establishes a swap line of 150 billion yuan (approximately \$24 billion), made it possible to transition to settlements in national currencies under a 30-year gas contract worth \$400 billion under the sanctions pressure of 2022-2026. By 2024-2025, the share of settlements in yuan and rubles in bilateral trade reached 90-95% (Fiam, 2025), and the total annual volume of such transactions is estimated at \$200-240 billion. Thus, one can see a trend toward the gradual transformation of such agreements from anti-crisis mechanisms into a permanent settlement infrastructure.

Another example is the China-Brazil Swap Agreement (People's daily online, 2025), which totals 190 billion yuan (\approx \$30 billion). This legal instrument ensured that the share of settlements in yuan and reals in bilateral trade exceeded 50 percent, the annual volume of which is estimated at \$150 billion. Notably, Brazil uses the yuan to pay for approximately 48% of its imports from China (New Central Asia, 2026), indicating the swap line's transition from a reserve mechanism to a regularly used payment instrument.

An additional level of cooperation is being fostered through collaboration between national development banks and the BRICS interbank cooperation mechanism. In October 2024, at the BRICS summit in Kazan, VEB.RF signed an updated framework cooperation agreement and separate agreements on credit lines in national currencies with partners from China and South Africa. The legal structure of these documents allows for the possible accession of Brazil and India, laying the foundation for transforming bilateral interbank relations into a multilateral project financing mechanism in national currencies (Rambler Finance, 2024).

A new trend demonstrating the transition from bilateral currency agreements to the formation of a next-generation multilateral treaty framework deserves special attention. This is the initiative promoted by the Reserve Bank of India to interconnect the digital currency systems of BRICS central banks (Tass, 2026) (the proposal is up for discussion at the 2026 summit). Essentially, this proposal represents the first formal draft of a multilateral agreement [13], aimed at ensuring the interoperability of the digital ruble, digital yuan, and digital rupee for cross-border settlements.

Thus, it can be seen that the current mechanisms are attempting to move from bilateral clearing to a multilateral settlement system, which qualitatively changes the legal nature of obligations and the degree of integration of the financial systems of the participating states.

[13] The legal novelty of this concept lies in the fact that it does not presuppose the creation of a supranational currency or a unified payment system, but is based on the principle of mutual recognition of national digital currencies and the harmonization of their circulation protocols. The technical mechanisms for implementation are settlement cycles, which allow for the netting of mutual claims, and currency swap lines as a tool for the final settlement of balances.

Problems and Prospects of Currency Integration

Having analyzed everything that has been said so far, the question naturally arises: is the lack of a universal codified legal basis for unification an obstacle to further monetary integration or, on the contrary, its conscious advantage?

As I have noted before, the absence of a single founding treaty and supranational mechanisms should not be seen as a weakness, but as a legal expression of the very nature of BRICS [14]. The prevalence of the soft law model allows each state to selectively join those initiatives that correspond to its national interests and capabilities.

On the other hand, despite significant progress, the existing model of monetary cooperation retains a number of structural limitations. The fragmented nature of the BRICS treaty framework creates systemic constraints on monetary integration. The predominance of bilateral swap lines instead of multilateral mechanisms leads to “network fragmentation” and excludes the possibility of multilateral netting of settlements [15].

There is no legally established mechanism for establishing a common currency basket and determining mutual exchange rates outside of the US dollar. The New Development Bank's mandate to lend in national currencies is limited by capital, and refinancing mechanisms have not yet been institutionalized. Furthermore, the procedure for new participants in the BRICS+ format to join existing currency instruments, including the Contingent Reserve Arrangement, has not been regulated. These factors point to the need for gradual institutional coordination of existing cooperation instruments.

The identified contradictions allow us to formulate prospects for the transition to currency integration within the existing legal framework. It appears that this evolution will not involve replacing flexible mechanisms with rigid ones, but rather their gradual institutionalization and mutual coordination. The most realistic scenario is the transformation of the Contingent Reserve Arrangement from a decentralized network of bilateral obligations into a system of collective liquidity management. This does not require a revision of the 2014 Agreement, but it does require the adoption of an additional protocol formalizing the decision-making procedure for the collective provision of funds and the distribution of shares to new participants. The second promising area is expanding the New Development Bank's issuing function. Currently, discussions are underway on the possibility of the NDB issuing debt

[14] The pluralism of legal systems and the uneven economic development of the participating states objectively make the model of rigid supranational integration along the lines of the European Union unviable.

[15] The Russia–China line of 150 billion yuan and the China–Brazil line of 190 billion yuan exist in parallel and are not linked into a single clearing system. This precludes the possibility of multilateral netting: India, which has a rupee surplus in its trade with Russia, cannot use these funds to settle Brazil's real deficit, as there is no legal mechanism for such a trilateral netting.

obligations denominated in BRICS special drawing rights—a standard unit of account pegged to a basket of currencies of the participating countries (Higher school of economics, 2023). The legal structure of such an instrument could be borrowed from the IMF, but with a fundamental difference: the issuer is not a supranational body, but an international organization controlled by the member states themselves. The third area concerns the contractual formalization of the payment infrastructure. The Indian initiative to interconnect central bank digital currency systems, proposed for the 2026 summit, represents the first draft of a multilateral agreement that does not create a supranational currency but ensures technical interoperability between national payment systems. If successful, this model could become a legal template for the inclusion of other states in the BRICS currency space without requiring them to join all of the association's institutions.

Conclusion

The analysis demonstrates that BRICS monetary cooperation is developing within a flexible and multi-layered legal model that combines soft law mechanisms, international treaty institutions, and a network of bilateral agreements. This model reflects the specific nature of the association, which is based on preserving the monetary sovereignty of its member states. From a theoretical perspective, the BRICS model may be described as a form of decentralized monetary governance based on contractual coordination rather than institutional hierarchy. This model represents an alternative pathway of international financial cooperation that differs significantly from classical integration models such as the European Union, where supranational institutions play a central role. The further evolution of BRICS monetary cooperation will likely be associated with the development of multilateral settlement mechanisms, digital payment technologies, and deeper institutional coordination of existing instruments. BRICS is therefore gradually developing a unique model of international monetary cooperation based not on supranational integration but on the contractual coordination of sovereign financial systems.

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